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Perceived Influence of School Calendar Policy on Management of Public Lower Basic Schools in North Central Nigeria

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***Abstract:** This study investigated the perceived influence of school calendar policy on management of public lower basic schools in North Central Nigeria. Two research questions guided the study and two hypotheses were formulated and tested for the study. The study adopted survey research design. The population of the study consists of all 110, 022 teachers from 12,775 public primary schools in the North Central Nigeria. The sample size for the study was 399 teachers. This sample was in line with Yamene (1970) formula for determining sample size. The study employed multi-stage sampling procedure which include purposive sampling technique, proportionate stratified sampling and accidental sampling technique. The instrument used for data collection was “a self-structured questionnaire titled “School Calendar Policy and Management of School Questionnaire (SCPMSQ)”. The instrument was validated by five experts with overall reliability coefficient of 0.82. Data collected were analyzed using Mean and Standard Deviation to answer the research questions, while chi-square goodness-of-fit was used to test hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study revealed that enrolment period and lesson periods have perceived influence on management of public secondary schools in North Central-Nigeria. Based on the findings of this study,*

it was recommended that government should ensure the timely allocation of funds based on enrolment projections. Schools with higher enrolment should receive additional resources, including textbooks, furniture and other learning materials. Also, school management should adjust the length of lesson periods based on the complexity of the subject matter and the age group of students. Pupils benefit from shorter, more focused sessions, while older students can handle longer periods.

Keywords: *School Calendar Policy, Management, Enrolment Period and Lesson Periods*

Introduction

In any organization or field of human endeavour, there must be a guide that supports its programmes. This guide usually comes in the form of policies, which help in guiding and directing how the organization can be effectively managed. A policy defines the areas in which decisions are to be made but does not make the decisions themselves. It typically provides a general framework that enhances decision-making. A policy is a written document or method established by law to guide a unit of action. According to Nzeako (2016), the objective of any policy is to satisfy individual needs, community pressures, and the degree of complexity and sophistication to which socialized personnel are educated and trained to meet these demands.

Efforts have been made to develop education in Nigeria since independence in 1960. Various policies related to education have been formulated such as the appointment of principal officers, funding, staff recruitment and quality assurance. Others are provision of facilities, curriculum, and academic programs. Other policies, such as the school calendar, teacher salary scale, teaching methods, curricular content, graduation requirements, school infrastructure investment, Joint Matriculation Examination Board (JAMB), and school calendar policy, also have a significant influence on educational policies in Nigeria. Unfortunately, these efforts appear not to have produced the desired stability in the educational sector, resulting in a deplorable condition. It is so bad that some resourceful Nigerians prefer to send their children to Europe, America, and even small African countries. Apart from the general problems of policy formulation and implementation common to most countries, especially those in the third world, some factors have been identified as peculiar to Nigeria and inhibiting its educational growth. Nigeria is known as the giant of Africa in terms of resourcefulness as a major oil and gas producer. Paradoxically, most Nigerians appear not to be educated due to the education policies introduced by the government.

Education policy comprises principles and guidelines formulated in the educational sphere, as well as a collection of laws and rules that govern the operation of education systems (Organization of Economic Community Development, 2017). Educational policies designed in the university education sector encompass school calendars, teacher salary scales, teaching methods, curricular content, graduation requirements, school infrastructure investment, and the values that schools are expected to uphold and model for various educational levels, including early childhood education, primary education, secondary education, and tertiary education (Yaro, 2018). Policy is necessary to guide the formulation of any educational reform. It is a process that enables the political process to acknowledge the reality and legitimacy of conflicting interests and desires among its participants. It provides guidance for properly directed and coordinated action towards the attainment of desired educational goals. The success of any educational system or reform in any nation depends on the policies put in place, how they are implemented, and how they are managed. Policies are generally adopted by a governing body

within an organization (Nweke, Muhammad, Chukwu, Uche, Madu & Ezurike, 2021). The implication is that educational policies enable effective and efficient management of school.

School management is a major focus in primary education. Educational management is the process of providing leadership within an educational system to coordinate activities and make decisions that lead to the attainment of the school's objectives, which are effective teaching and learning (Adeyemi, 2010). The school head teacher needs to coordinate the activities of the school to achieve these objectives and must be equipped with the necessary skills and knowledge to perform their duties. Management involves the judicious utilization of human, material, financial, and time resources to achieve organizational goals or objectives (Akpakwu, 2013). Effective management school ensures efficiency and effectiveness in the use of available resources while overcoming any constraints that might hinder the achievement of objectives of school management.

Furthermore, school management involves leading the school towards development through the optimal use of human and material resources, physical resources, and principles necessary for achieving the school's objectives. School management takes into account all aspects of the school, including policies, material and human resources, activities, and equipment, integrating them to achieve educational goals (Ugochukwu, Akueyinwa & Ndubueze, 2022). The management of primary school education involves various activities, such as planning school calendars, organizing examinations, tests and assessments, content coverage, extra-curricular activities, pupils' academic performance, school attendance, and enrolment (Agih, 2015). However, the management of lower basic schools depends on the educational policies put in place by the Federal Republic of Nigeria. One of the policies that appear to influence the management of primary school is the school calendar policy.

A school calendar is a policy that defines the academic year, the period during which an educational institution holds classes or lessons. It determines when schools enrol pupils, when lessons start, the duration (in hours or minutes) of lessons, the scheduling of co-curricular activities, assessment periods, and holiday schedules (Stark Education Partnership, 2018). School calendar policy, often set by the government, has a significant impact on how schools are managed and operated. The school calendar in Nigeria is divided into three terms, which can range from as short as ten (10) weeks to as long as thirteen (13) weeks for primary school (Oyemwinmina & Aibieyi, 2015). This calendar governs the activities within the school system. Officially, the school calendar in Nigeria is structured into three divisions/quarters known as terms. The school calendar has a significant influence on school management systems, impacting areas such as the conduct of school examinations, school attendance, tests and assessments, and learner enrolment. According to Oyemwinmina and Aibieyi (2015), a school calendar is an official list of dates and deadlines found at the beginning of the school year. It specifies the dates for terms, enrolment periods, examination periods, holidays, and periods when classes are not in session. This calendar includes registration dates, class start dates, add/drop deadlines, exam dates, and more. However, this study primarily focuses on the components of the school calendar as identified by DeLeon, Varela and Jones (2022). These components include lesson periods and enrolment periods.

Enrolment period in schools refers to the specific timeframe during which pupils, both new and returning, are allowed to register for classes or programs for an upcoming academic term or school year. This period can vary depending on the type of educational institution and the level of education. In discussing the school calendar, Oyemwinmina and Aibieyi (2015) identified the enrolment date of pupils as an aspect of school calendar policy in Nigeria. The registration period occupies a vital role in the management of schools, as it allows the school administration to ascertain the actual number of

enrolled pupils. The school calendar has the potential to affect the enrolment of pupils in schools. Patterson and King (2014) argue that the school calendar policy in Nigeria, which starts the academic year in September, often discourages enrolment as this period coincides with the harvest season for groundnut, rice, and other agricultural products in many states in North Central Nigeria. Winkelmann (2014) which found that year-round scheduling is cost-effective and increases building utilization. The study also indicated that both year-round and traditional calendars contribute to higher job satisfaction levels among teachers. In addition, Holly (2016) who reported that school enrolment size has a small but not substantial effect on average students' academic achievement. Enrolment of pupils usually provides opportunities for school management to design time for the commencement of lessons in the school.

A lesson period is a specific amount of time allocated for teaching or instruction within an educational setting. The duration of a lesson period can vary depending on the educational institution, grade level, and subject being taught. In many cases, a standard lesson period is around 45 minutes to an hour, but it can be shorter or longer. The length of lesson periods in primary school has a profound impact on the management of these institutions and their overall effectiveness. According to Baker, Fabrega, Galindo, and Mishook (2014), the duration of these lessons is a critical factor that significantly shapes the efficiency of teaching and learning. However, despite its simplistic appearance, the class period in a secondary school setting is a complex issue. This is because the amount of time actually spent in the classroom on teaching and learning tasks depends on its relationship to the curriculum and teaching quality (Baker et al., 2014). However, the amount of time spent in class depends on the notion of the lesson period, which typically gravitates by the school calendar towards achieving its desired target for that particular school term. The allocation of 35-40 minutes of class periods by the National Policy on Education seems to make pupils' achievement difficult due to the number of additional factors that affect pupils' learning, ranging from a teacher's effectiveness to the education policy of the nation (Igbojinwaekwu, 2013). Ukpong and George (2013) who discovered that pupils' academic achievement was positively affected by longer lesson periods, as these allowed teachers to cover more topics. Similarly, Anibasa (2015) found that lesson periods enable school management to effectively monitor classroom activities and help teachers prepare and teach more efficiently. Lesson period patterns are the configurations of days and hours to be used in setting up the class activities in school. The lesson period is a function of how all class resources are managed. These resources include teachers, classrooms, and pupils.

These challenges to pose by school calendar policy on the management of public lower basic schools in North Central Nigeria appear to be rooted in Nigeria's historical struggles to establish an effective educational system. Despite the formulation of educational policies, such as the school calendar, by various governments, their successful implementation has been hindered by political instability. This instability has, in turn, deterred the political will necessary to execute these policies. With frequent changes in government leadership and a climate of uncertainty, policy continuity becomes a major challenge. It appears that every political player is eager to make their mark before being replaced by another group, further complicating the situation. As a result, educational policy implementation in Nigeria has been significantly impacted (Okoroma, 2010).

One significant consequence of this unstable school calendar policy is that many pupils who are supposed to be enrolling in and attending school often find themselves roaming the streets. The specific timing outlined in the school calendar for school resumption coincides with periods when many parents prefer to send their children to engage in street vending or work on farms. Consequently, the policy appears to impede the comprehensive coverage of academic content, the proper

administration of tests and assessments, and the academic performance of pupils in schools. Teachers frequently find themselves grappling with the challenge of insufficient time to cover their syllabus, as the school calendar mandates the start of each term. This situation could be applicable to the management of primary schools in North Central Nigeria, which is what has motivated the researcher to investigate the influence of school calendar policy on the management of primary education in North central, Nigeria with particular focus on enrolment period, lesson periods, examination periods, holiday periods, extra-curricular date management and duration of terms.

Statement of the Problem

Education is a key to the development of any nation. It is also one of the greatest investments that a nation could use for the quick development of its economic, political, sociological, and human resources. As the oldest industry, it is the main instrument used by society to preserve, maintain and upgrade its status. In every educational system, the preparation of the young ones to face future challenges and develop them to meet the nation's manpower requirements remains the major objective. However, several policies formulated by various governments seem to thwart this effort. One such policy is the school calendar.

The policy of the school calendar appear to become a global debate due to its influence on the management of schools, especially at the secondary school level. The underlying issues cause pupils to exhibit low academic achievement and eventually drop out of school. These complex issues are related to pupils, teachers, other school personnel, and the learning environment. The enrolment of pupils in primary school which possibly influence management in areas like the time allocated for teaching and learning. This is the reason why many teachers complain about their inability to cover the syllabus within the limited time allocated for teaching and learning. The school calendar appears to affect pupils' academic performance in primary school. Parents often complain about their children's poor performance in tests and assessments, which could be attributed to teachers' inability to cover the syllabus in school.

Today, it is challenging for many schools because allocated time for schools to conduct teaching and learning activities appears to significantly influence the academic performance of secondary school pupils. This perhaps manifest from inadequate time that is usually given to teachers to prepare for lessons to teach and pupils to concentrate or read and prepare for examinations. The problem of this study is put in a question form thus: What is the perceived influence of school calendar policy on the management of public lower basic schools in North Central, Nigeria?

Objective of the Study

The objective of this study was to investigate perceived influence of school calendar policy on the management of public lower basic schools in North Central, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to;

1. Ascertain perceived influence of enrolment period on the management of public lower basic schools in North Central-Nigeria.
2. Establish influence of lesson periods on the management of public lower basic schools in North Central-Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study;

1. What is the perceived influence of enrolment period on the management of public lower basic schools in North-Central Nigeria?

2. What is the perceived influence of lesson periods on the management of public lower basic schools in North-Central Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance;

1. Enrolment period has no significant perceived influence on the management of public lower basic schools in North Central-Nigeria.
2. Lesson periods have no significant perceived influence on the management of public lower basic schools in North Central-Nigeria.

Methodology

This study employed survey research design. This is a type of design that gather data from a large number of subjects from a representative sample of the population. The population of the study consists of all 110, 022 teachers from 12, 775 public primary schools in the North Central Nigeria. The sample size for the study is 399 teachers from a population of 110,022 teachers in 12,775 public primary schools in North Central Nigeria. This sample is in line with Yamene (1970) formula for determining sample size. The study employed multi-stage sampling procedure. In this study the following sampling techniques was used: purposive sampling technique, proportionate stratified sampling and accidental sampling technique in different stages.

The instrument for data collection was questionnaire titled “School Calendar Policy and Management of School Questionnaire (SCPMSQ)”. It was divided into two sections, Sections A and B. Section A which contained instruction to the respondents, while Section B contained a total number of 10 items divided in two clusters. Cluster A contained items 1-5 which focused on the enrolment period and management, and Cluster B included items 6-10, which gathered information on lesson periods and management. The instrument was structured on a four-point rating scale with response options of Strongly Agree (SA) = 4, Agree (A) = 3, Disagree (D) = 2, and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1. It was validated by five experts. Two experts in Measurement and Evaluation, Department of Guidance and Counselling and one expert in Educational Administration and Planning, Department of Educational Administration and Planning, College of Education, Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Makurdi and two in Educational Management, Department of Educational Foundations, Faculty of Education, Benue State University, Makurdi with reliability coefficient of enrolment period and management=0.88 and lesson periods and management=0.78 and the reliability coefficient of 0.82 was considered high enough and reliable. The descriptive statistics of Mean Scores and Standard Deviation were used to answer the research questions. The decision rule was based on the real limit of numbers $4+3+2+1=10/4=2.50$. The chi-square test of goodness of fit was used to test the null hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the perceived influence of enrolment period on the management of public lower basic schools in North Central Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean Scores and Standard Deviations on Perceived Influence of Enrolment Period on Management of Public Lower Basic Schools in North Central Nigeria

Item No	Item Description	N	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	Std	Decision
1	Time schedule for admitting new entrance into the school does not give teachers opportunity to plan for them.	380	175	140	52	13	3.26	0.82	Agree
2	When teachers are not consulted before entrant exams are conducted, it could affect their duties.	380	210	141	12	17	3.43	0.76	Agree
3	The August month set for conduct of new entrance examination enables head teachers to plan for their resumption in school.	380	105	173	78	24	2.94	0.86	Agree
4	The common entrants examination date set by the Ministry of Education for schools does not give teachers enough time to organize for academic activities.	380	105	243	16	16	3.15	0.68	Agree
5	The period set by the Ministry of Education for schools admitting new learners enables teachers to provide the needed facilities for them.	380	140	170	48	22	3.13	0.84	Agree
Cluster Mean & Std							3.18	0.79	Agree

Table 1 shows the mean scores of items 1-5 as 3.26, 3.43, 2.94, 3.15 and 3.13 with corresponding Standard Deviations of 0.82, 0.76, 0.86, 0.68 and 0.84 respectively. All the items were rated above the criterion mean of 2.50. The cluster mean of 3.18 and Standard Deviation of 0.79 which is above the cut-off point of 2.50 is agreed that there is perceived influence of enrolment period on the management of public lower basic schools in North Central Nigeria.

Research Question 2: What is the perceived influence of lesson periods on management of public lower basic schools in North Central Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean Scores and Deviations on Perceived Influence of Lesson Periods on Management of Public Lower Basic Schools in North Central Nigeria

Item No	Item Description	N	SA	A	D	SD	\bar{X}	Std	Decision
6	The thirty-five minutes allocated for teaching a subject in primary schools is enough for effective teaching.	380	207	141	19	13	3.43	0.74	Agree
7	Teachers cannot effectively execute lesson plan within forty minutes in senior primary schools.	380	242	105	23	10	3.52	0.73	Strongly Agree
8	The system of double periods for mathematics on timetable could affect organizing playing period for pupils.	380	242	107	21	10	3.53	0.72	Strongly Agree
9	The activity based teaching could take a lot of time which extends into preps periods.	380	140	209	15	16	3.24	0.72	Agree
10	Teaching pupils in the afternoon affects their attention span that will lead to noise making thereby affecting other activities in the school.	380	141	206	15	18	3.24	0.74	Agree
Cluster Mean & Std							3.39	0.73	Agree

Table 2 shows the mean scores of items 6-10 as 3.43, 3.52, 3.53, 3.24 and 3.24 with corresponding Standard Deviations of 0.74, 0.73, 0.72, 0.72 and 0.74 respectively. All the items were rated above the criterion mean of 2.50. The cluster mean of 3.39 and Standard Deviation of 0.73 which is above the cut-off point of 2.50 is agreed that lesson periods have perceived influence on management of public lower basic schools in North Central Nigeria.

Hypothesis 1: Enrolment period has no significant perceived influence on management of public lower basic schools in North Central Nigeria.

Table 3: Chi-square Analysis on Significant Perceived Influence of Enrolment Period on Management of Public Lower Basic Schools in North Central Nigeria

	SA	A	D	SD	Total	Df	Sig. Level	χ^2	P. Value	Decision
Observed	147	173	41	19						

Frequency										
					380	3	0.05	178.93 _a	0.00	Sig.
Expected Frequency	95.0	95.0	95.0	95.0						

P<0.05

Table 3 reveals that the Chi-square calculated value of 178.93, Df = 3 and a P-value of 0.00 which is less than alpha-value (α) of 0.05 (P<0.05), therefore, the null hypothesis which states that enrolment period has no significant perceived influence on management of public lower basic schools in North Central Nigeria is rejected. This shows that enrolment period has significant perceived influence on management of public lower basic schools in North Central Nigeria.

Hypothesis 2: Lesson periods have no significant perceived influence on management of public lower basic schools in North Central Nigeria.

Table 4: Chi-square Analysis on Perceived Influence of Lesson Periods on Management of Public Lower Basic Schools in North Central Nigeria.

	SA	A	D	SD	Total	Df	Sig. Level	χ^2	P. Value	Decision
Observed	194	154	19	13						
					380	3	0.05	285.90 _a	0.00	Sig.
Expected	95.0	95.0	95.0	95.0						

P<0.05

Table 4 indicates that the Chi-square calculated value of 285.90, Df = 3 and a P-value of 0.00 which is less than alpha-value (α) of 0.05 (P<0.05), therefore, the null hypothesis which states that lesson periods have no significant perceived influence on management of public lower basic schools in North Central Nigeria is rejected. This implies that lesson periods have significant perceived influence on management of public lower basic schools in North Central Nigeria.

Discussions

The findings revealed that the enrolment period has a perceived influence on management of public lower basic schools in North Central Nigeria. This result aligns with the research by Winkelmann (2014) which found that year-round scheduling is cost-effective and increases building utilization. The study also indicated that both year-round and traditional calendars contribute to higher job satisfaction levels among teachers. This is because these schedules allow teachers time to review their work during school days and feel refreshed after breaks. However, the study also found that pupils enrolled in both year-round and traditional schools are at risk for poor academic achievement due to various factors, including poverty and ethnic background. This finding is consistent with Holly (2016) who reported that school enrolment size has a small but not substantial effect on average students' academic achievement. The study also discovered that the enrolment size of school are reduced because of certain factors such as enrolment period specified by school authorities. The researcher further

reported that school enrolment size shrinks considerably for small town and rural areas respectively. This result is in this way because that time schedule for admitting new entrance into the school does not give teachers opportunity to plan for them and when teachers are not consulted before entrant exams are conducted and this affected their duties. They agreed that the August month set for conduct of new entrance examination enable head teachers to plan for their resumption in school and also, the common entrants' examination date set by the Ministry of Education for schools does not give teachers enough time to organize for academic activities. They agreed that the period set by the Ministry of Education for schools admitting new learners enables teachers to provide the needed facilities for them. In the opinion of the researcher, this finding therefore indicates that enrolment period plays a critical role in shaping the management of public primary schools in North Central Nigeria. Effective enrolment management allows for better resource allocation, teacher distribution, infrastructure development, and educational quality. Poorly managed enrolment periods, however, lead to overcrowded classrooms, strained resources, and decreased educational outcomes, thereby affecting the overall quality of primary education.

The results showed that lesson periods have perceived influence on management of public lower basic schools in North Central Nigeria. This finding aligns with the research by Ukpong and George (2013) who discovered that pupils' academic achievement was positively affected by longer lesson periods, as these allowed teachers to cover more topics. Similarly, Anibasa (2015) found that lesson periods enable school management to effectively monitor classroom activities and help teachers prepare and teach more efficiently. Anibasa further reported that lesson periods allow teachers to allocate their time effectively to cover the content of each topic and record it in their diaries. Additionally, it highlighted the importance of maintaining a class size of no more than 40-45 pupils to ensure effective evaluation and management. This result is like this because the thirty-five minutes allocated for teaching a subject in primary schools is enough for effective teaching. According to the study teachers cannot effectively execute lesson plan within forty minutes in senior primary schools and the system of double periods for mathematics on timetable could affect organizing playing period for pupils. The activity based teaching could take a lot of time which extends into preps periods. Teaching pupils in the afternoon affects their attention span that will lead to noise making thereby affecting other activities in the school. In the opinion of the researcher, this finding therefore means that properly structured lesson periods ensure efficient use of time and resources, promote balanced teacher workloads, improve student engagement, and support the broader curriculum goals. On the other hand, poorly managed lesson periods can disrupt learning, reduce teacher productivity, and limit the effectiveness of school management. Therefore, effective and efficient lesson plan period enable and adjusted to meet the needs of both students and teachers while aligning with educational policies and community expectations.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that school calendar policy such as enrolment period and lesson periods have perceived influence on management of public lower basic schools in North Central Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Government should ensure the timely allocation of funds based on enrolment projections. Schools with higher enrolment should receive additional resources, including textbooks, furniture, and other learning materials. Align teacher recruitment and deployment with enrolment periods to

avoid teacher shortages and overcrowded classrooms. This can be achieved by engaging with parents and communities to better understand the factors affecting enrolment decisions.

2. School management should adjust the length of lesson periods based on the complexity of the subject matter and the age group of students. Pupils benefit from shorter, more focused sessions, while older learners can handle longer periods. This can be achieved by implementing pilot programmes to test different lesson period structures and analyzing their impact on pupils' performance and teacher effectiveness. Use the results to make data-driven decisions.

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